

Synthesis of 3-Amino-1,4-diarylazetid-2-ones. Part-II¹

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Monocyclic β -lactams like nocordacin², possess good antibacterial properties. The azetid-2-one ring system is the main structural feature of monocyclic and bicyclic β -lactam antibiotics³.

In the present communication, the synthesis of some 3-amino-1, 4-diarylazetid-2-ones, via ketene/imine cycloaddition reaction⁴ is reported. The 3-amino- β -lactams are quarternised⁵ to give quarternary ammonium- β -lactams. Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde is condensed with *m*-chloroaniline to give 3-chloro-*N*-(2-thieryl)-methylenebenzenamine⁶ (**1**). The Schiff bases (**2-4**) are prepared similarly by using corresponding aldehydes and amines. Phthalimidoacetyl chloride is treated with the four imines (**1-4**) in the presence of triethylamine to produce the corresponding 3-phthalimidoyl-1,4-diarylazetid-2-ones; (**5-8** Scheme 1). Hydrazinolysis⁷ of **5-8** with 95% hydrazine gives the corresponding 3-amino-1,4-diarylazetid-2-ones (**9-12**). Quarternisation of **9-12** with methyl iodide in the presence of tripropylamine produces the corresponding 3-quarternary ammonium-1,4-diarylazetid-2-ones (**13-16**).

The compounds (Table 1) have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, uv, ir and nmr spectral data. The optical rotation of compounds **5**, **7**, **9**, **11**, **13**, **15** reveals that they are racemic mixtures.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-360-L (60 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and uv spectra on a Beckman-26 spectrophotometer.

Substituted-N-(2-thienyl)methylene-benzenamine

(**1-2**) : Thiophene-2-aldehyde (0.1 mol) was refluxed with appropriate amine (0.1 mol) in benzene (100 ml) in a Dean and Stark apparatus till theoretical amount of water was removed. The residue after the removal of benzene was extracted with hexane. Hexane was distilled off and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol : **1** (78%), m.p. 67°; **2** (72%) 72°; λ_{\max} 334, 275 nm; ν_{\max} 1 640 cm⁻¹ (CH=N); δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (6H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃), 2.85 (1H, m, *J* 8 Hz, CH), 6.95-7.7 (7H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N).

Substituted-N-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)methylene-benzenamine (3-4) : 3,4,5-Trimethoxybenzaldehyde (0.1 mol) was refluxed with appropriate amine (0.1 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) for 45 min. The mixture was cooled to 10° and the solid separated was crystallised from ethanol (80%): **3**, m.p. 82°; λ_{\max} 314 nm; ν_{\max} 1 640 (CH=N), 1 160 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ (CDCl₃) 3.9 (9H, s, OCH₃), 7.05-7.3 (6H, m, ArH), 8.29 (1H, s, CH=N); *m/z* *M*⁺ 305 (100% base); **4**, 75°; 324 nm; ν_{\max} 1 640 (CH=N), 1 160 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ (CDCl₃) 1.25 (6H, a, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃), 2.8 (1H, m, *J* 8 Hz, CH), 3.9 (9H, s, OCH₃), 6.8-7.4 (6H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N).

3-Phthalimidoyl-1,4-diarylazetid-2-ones (5-8) : To a mixture of the appropriate Schiff bases (**1-4**; 0.04 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) dissolved in dry benzene (80 ml), phthalimidoacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) in benzene (50 ml) was added dropwise with stirring for 1.5 h. The mixture was stirred for 1 h when triethylammonium chloride separated, which was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and the remaining viscous liquid was digested with a mixture of *n*-hexane and diethyl ether (1 : 1; 3 × 30 ml). The resulting solid was digested with ethanol (200 ml) for 1.5 h; then cooled,

	R ₁	R ₂
1, 5, 9, 13	2-Thienyl	3-Chlorophenyl
2, 6, 10, 14	2-Thienyl	4-isopropylphenyl
3, 7, 11, 15	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	3-Chlorophenyl
4, 8, 12, 16	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	4-Isopropylphenyl.

Scheme 1. Reagent : (i) Triethylamine, (ii) N₂H₄ and (iii) CH₃I, tripropylamine.

filtered and the solid was crystallised from dioxane : water (1 : 1) : **5** (48%), m.p. 194°, λ_{\max} 239; ν_{\max} 1 760 (C=O β -lactum), 1 725 cm⁻¹ (C=O phthalimido); δ_4 (CDCl₃) 5.3 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, C-H Azing), 6.8–7.9 (11H, m, ArH); **6** (57%), 215°; λ_{\max} 239 nm; ν_{\max} 1 760 (C=O B-lactam), 1 720 cm⁻¹ (C=O phthalimido); δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (6H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃), 2.8 (1H, m, *J* 8 Hz, CH), 5.4 (1H, d, *J* 3 HZ, C₄-H, Az ring), 5.6 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, C₃-H Az ring), 6.8–7.9 (11H, m, ArH); **7** (52%), 208°; λ_{\max} 241 nm; β_{\max} 1 770 (C=O β -lactam), 1 720 cm⁻¹ (C=O phthalimido); *m/z* 492, *M*⁺; 345 (100% base) δ (CDCl₃) 3.75 (9H, s, OCH₃), 5.3 (2H, s, C₃ and C₄ Az ring), 6.6–7.9 (10H, m, ArH); **8** (41%), 228°; λ_{\max} 239 nm; ν_{\max} 1 780 (C=O B-lactam), 1 720 (C=O phthalimido); δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (6H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃), 2.8 (1H, m, *J* 3 Hz, CH), 3.8 (9H, s, OCH₃), 5.3 (2H, s, C₃ and C₄-H Az ring).

3-Amino-1,4-diarylazetidines (9-12) : The appropriate 3-phthalimidoyl-1,4-diarylazetidines (5-8 ; 0.001 mol) was stirred with a methanolic solution of 95% hydrazine (0.004 mol) in methylene chloride (50 ml) at room temperature. The precipitated phthalhydrazide was filtered off. The filtrate was washed with water (3 × 50 ml) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Methylene chloride was then evaporated to give a solid which was triturated with ether (50 ml). Evaporation of ether gave the product which was crystallised from benzene : **9** (82%), m.p. 67°; λ_{\max} 243 nm; ν_{\max} 1 760 cm⁻¹ (C=O β -lactam); δ (CDCl₃) 2.33–2.66 (2H, br, NH₂), 4.2 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, C₃-H Az ring), 4.9 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, C₄-H Az ring), 6.9–7.5 (7H, m, ArH); **10** (83%), 75°; λ_{\max} 248 nm; ν_{\max} 3 500–3 200 br (NH₂), 1 760 cm⁻¹ (C=O β -lactam); δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (6H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃), 2.0–2.5 (2H, br, NH₂), 2.85 (1H, m, *J* 8 Hz, CH), 4.2 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, C₃-H Az ring), 4.95 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, C₄-H Az ring), 6.95–7.5 (7H, m, ArH); **11** (77%), 64°; λ_{\max} 247 nm; ν_{\max} 1 760 cm⁻¹ (C=O β -lactam); δ (CDCl₃) 2.3–3.0 (2H, br, NH₂), 3.8 (9H, s, OCH₃), 4.0 (d, *J* 3 Hz, C₃-H, Az ring), 4.6 (d, *J* 3 Hz, C₄-H Az ring), 6.4–7.4 (7H, m, ArH); *m/z* 362 *M*⁺, 306 (100% base peak); **12** (71%), 68°; λ_{\max} 246 nm; ν_{\max} 3 600–3, 200 br (NH₂). 1 760 cm⁻¹ (C=O β -lactam); δ (CDCl₃) 1.25 (6H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃),

2.8 (1H, m, 8 Hz, CH), 3.8 (9H, s, OCH₃), 2.1–3.0 (2H, br, NH₂), 4.0 (1H, s, C₃-H Az ring), 4.6 (1H, s, C₄-H) Az ring, 6.6–7.5 (6H, m, ArH).

(1,4-Diarylazetid-2-on-3-yl) trimethylammonium iodide (**13-16**) : To a mixture of the appropriate 3-amino-1, 4-diarylazetid-2-one (**9-12**; 0.005 mol) and tripropylamine (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethyl acetate (10 ml), methyl iodide (0.015 mol) was added dropwise with stirring for 1.5 h. The resulting solid was digested with acetone (5 ml) and crystallised from ethanol : **13** (92%), m.p. 198°; λ_{\max} 250 nm; ν_{\max} 1 790 (C=O β -lactam); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.4 (9H, s, N-CH₃), 4.33 (1H, s, C₄-H Az ring), 5.5 (1H, s, C₃-H, Az ring), 6.9–7.6 (7H, m, ArH); **14** (86%), 220°; λ_{\max} 240 nm; ν_{\max} 1 800 cm⁻¹ (C=O β -lactam); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.2 (6H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃), 3.3 (9H, s, N-CH₃), 2.8 (1H, m, *J* 8 Hz, CH), 4.3 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, C₄-H Az ring), 5.3 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, C₃-H Az ring), 6.6–7.6 (7H, m, ArH); **15** (89%), 200°; λ_{\max} 245 nm; λ_{\max} 1 760 cm⁻¹ (C=O β -lactam); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.3 (9H, s, N-CH₃), 3.6 (9H, s, OCH₃), 5.3 (1H, s, C₄-H Az ring), 6.1 (1H, s, C₃-H Az ring), 6.9–7.4 (6H, m, ArH); **16** (91%), 225°; λ_{\max} 243 nm; ν_{\max} 1 800 cm⁻¹ (C=O β -lactam); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.25 (6H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH₃), 2.8 (1H, m, *J*

8 Hz, CH), 3.3 (9H, s, N-CH₃), 3.7 (9H, s, OCH₃), 5.2 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, C₄-H Az ring), 6.05 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, C₃-H Az ring), 6.9–7.4 (6H, m, ArH).

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